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Sleeves of Death: Thanatopolitics and Disposable Bodies in *Altered Carbon*

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Abstract:

This paper explores a critical examination of thanatopolitics, necropolitics and posthumanism in Richard K. Morgan's *Altered Carbon* (2002), especially the devaluation and disposal of bodies in a highly technologically advanced yet morally rendered society. In the novel, consciousness is made digital and stored in stacks and bodies, often referred to as "sleeves" that turned into replaceable commodities. This extreme separation of oneself from the body produces a new kind of biopolitical control through which capital and social class determine access to immortality. Drawing on Achille Mbembe's theory of Necropolitics, this research examines how the state and corporate elites exert control over death, thereby leveraging the bodies of the disenfranchised as scenes of violence, labour and surveillance. Through characters like Takeshi Kovacs- death-row inmate and Elizabeth Elliot, the novel reveals a dystopia where the poor are trapped in endless resurrection and exploitation while the wealthy transcend corporeal mortality. The paper uses theories to examine how digital immortality reiterates neoliberal hierarchies and intensifies the reach of surveillance capitalism. Transformation revealing the inevitable intersection of technology, power and death in the posthuman world, *Altered Carbon* comes to be a speculative critique of techno-utopian hope. The political and ethical frameworks of digital disembodiment are questioned in this

research alongside a paradigm of physical disposability in contemporary life and speculative fiction.

Keywords: Thanatopolitics, Necropolitics, Posthumanism, Digital Immortality, Disposable Bodies, Surveillance Capitalism.

Introduction

What occurs when death is a market-controlled privilege rather than a natural equaliser? The human body becomes yet another disposable asset in an excellent techno-capitalist economy in an era where digital consciousness may be recorded, transferred and traded. A seminal cyberpunk novel later made into a Netflix series (2018-2020), Richard K. Morgan's *Altered Carbon* (2002) presents such a future with striking clarity. Set in the 25th century, the story follows Takeshi Kovacs, an ex-soldier turned investigator, as he travels a world where human brains are kept on cortical stacks- disk-like devices lodged at the base of the skull and passed between physical bodies termed as 'sleeves'. While the rich attain practical immortality via this technology, the poor are victims of bodily dispossession, identity fragmentation and systemic violence.

Deeply interacting with the biopolitical and posthuman condition, Morgan's novel deconstructs conventional notions of the human body, mortality and subjectivity. *Altered Carbon* essentially examines a world in which thanatopolitics- the governance and control over death, has been reshaped. Originally based on Michel Foucault's ideas of biopolitics and further expanded by Achille Mbembe's lens of necropolitics, the idea challenges how power determines- who gets to live and who must die? "The ultimate expression of sovereignty resides, to a large degree, in the power and the capacity to dictate who may live and who must die" (Mbembe 11). Death is a commodified result, stratified by wealth, race and social level in Morgan's speculative future.

The underclass, such as immigrants, prisoners, sex workers are subjected to forced re-sleeving, physical abuse and existential erasure, while the elites, sometimes known as ‘Meths’ (Methuselahs), keep their minds over the centuries by transferring consciousness into cloned or altered bodies. Deprived of significance and autonomy, these bodies mirror Giorgio Agamben's notion of ‘bare life’, lives reduced to only biological existence, lacking political or legal rights. “The protagonist of this book is bare life.....the realm of bare life-which is originally situated at the margins of the political order-gradually begins to coincide with the political realm, and exclusion and inclusion, outside and inside, bios and zoe, right and fact, enter into a zone of irreducible indistinction” (Agamben 8,9). Particularly on those deprived of autonomy, bodily identity gets fragmented, unstable and usually enforced in this world. In the techno-future, bodies are disposable products- rented, abused and discarded- rather than sacred vessels.

Moreover, the paper explores posthuman queries on consciousness, embodiment and the morals of digital life. Using thinkers like Rosi Braidotti and N. Katherine Hayles, *Altered Carbon* challenges the coherence of the self, when removed from the body by blurring the distinction between human and machine, biological and artificial. Reflecting the necropolitical systems ingrained in global capitalism, surveillance systems and biotechnology, the novel works as a speculative metaphor for our modern society. The following central issues are addressed in this research paper: How does *Altered Carbon* portray a thanatopolitical administration that governs bodies and death? In what ways does the narrative expose the commodification and disposability of marginalised bodies in a posthuman context? Moreover, viewed through the lens of necropolitics and embodiment, how does the work criticise techno-capitalist dreams of eternity?

Literature Review

Richard K. Morgan's *Altered Carbon* has emerged as a key book for scholars exploring transhumanism, digital consciousness and the ethics of technological advancement. Set in a future where human consciousness is digitized into 'cortical stacks' and transferred between disposable bodies or 'sleeves'.

A significant strand of scholarship addresses the radical mind-body dualism that the novel presents. Lakshay Kumar Kamboj, in "ALTERED DISTINCTION: A CRITICAL STUDY OF THE MIND AND THE BODY IN THE CASE OF ALTERED CARBON", using Cartesian philosophy, argues that the separation of consciousness from the body is the mechanism by which bodies are devalued and commodified. Nikola Foršek supports this view in "Transhumanism, Ethics and Religion in *Altered Carbon*", noting the body is reduced to a "dispensable piece of clothing," stripped of its sanctity.

Syed Abuzar Naqvi and colleagues further explore in "EXPLORING IDENTITY AND CONSCIOUSNESS IN RICHARD K MORGAN'S ALTERED CARBON A TRANS HUMANIST PERSPECTIVE"- disembodiment from a transhumanist perspective, analysing how identity remains psychologically continuous despite being untethered from any singular, biological form. The research argues that *Altered Carbon* redefines the notion of selfhood, portraying it as fluid and technologically extended, while also placing the novel within a broader transhumanist discourse around digital immortality, human enhancement and body commodification.

Building on this, critics like Johannes Wally and Foršek have analysed how commodification reinforces deep socio-economic divides. Wally, in "Narrative Conflict and Implied Value Conflict: An Analysis of Aspects of the Implied Worldview of Richard Morgan's *Altered Carbon* (2002) and Hanif Kureishi's *The Body* (2002)"- identifies the

protagonist's movement. Foršek points to the Meths' ability to "own" human beings, reflecting extreme power imbalances which highlights how even death offers no escape from control.

While existing studies engage thoroughly with transhumanist themes, identity and class stratification, they rarely contextualise these within a political framework of power and death. This paper addresses that gap by applying Achille Mbembe's necropolitics to argue that *Altered Carbon* envisions a world where sovereignty is exercised through the systematic production of disposable bodies- a fully realized thanatopolitical regime.

The Techno-Thanatopolitical Order

The strongest form of governance in Morgan's *Altered Carbon* is not over life but over death. The novel projects a future where a person's consciousness is retained in tiny gadgets implanted in the spinal cord called cortical stacks, so that it may be re-sleeved into new bodies. This invention creates a society where death, once the ultimate human limit, has become a market-regulated privilege. In techno- thanatopolitical world of *Altered Carbon*, people are nothing if they don't have re-sleeving insurance, as the main character Takeshi Kovacs considers- "Economic crisis. You know how it is. One day you own a house, your sleeve policy's paid up, the next you're on the street looking at a single lifespan" (Morgan 105). Lieutenant Ortega discusses how the very wealthy, or 'Meths', perceive life and death differently: "You live that long, things start happening to you. You get too impressed with yourself. Ends up, you think you're God. Suddenly the little people, thirty, maybe forty years old, well they don't really matter anymore" (Morgan 65). This has scary consequences: while immortality is set aside for the privileged elite, actual death results from economic exclusion.

This arrangement is a perfect example of Achille Mbembe's necropolitics theory, which specifies that sovereignty is the ability to decide who may live and who has to perish. In *Altered Carbon*, transhuman elites known as Meths- who have the wealth to infinitely clone and re-

sleeve themselves having this sovereign authority. This privatisation of death shows what scholar Zachary Catanzaro says: “these mechanisms already function, creating domains where living populations exist under sophisticated technologies of exclusion and deduction” (52). The Meths’ capacity to overcome death mirrors Foucault’s claim that biopower governs populations by controlling life processes, but in this instance, power reaches even further-over death itself. This notion of Foucault’s study on biopower and modern sovereignty is compared to Achille Mbembe’s (2003) notion of ‘necropolitics’ shifting the focus from the management of life to the management of death, as the right “to make live and let die”(Gebhardt).

The thanatopolitical architecture is clearly evident in how the affluent abuse the poor’s bodies. The market in sleeves allows the elite to inhabit youthful or enhanced bodies, whereas the working class is subjected to forced re-sleeving, possibly into bodies of varying genders, ages or ethnic origins. This reflects Giorgio Agamben’s notion of ‘bare life’, in which people live outside of the protection of law, exposed to death without redress. In the release hall of the justice facility, Takeshi Kovacs witnesses a family reunion. The scene powerfully illustrates, the trauma and confusion are immediate. The younger child is terrified and cannot recognise her father, repeatedly asking, “Where’s Daddy? Where’s Daddy?” (Morgan 261). The young woman’s face is described as “a mask of shock” (Morgan 261). The re-sleeved man himself is weeping, highlighting the shared trauma of the experience. This scene directly demonstrates how the technology of re-sleeving, a supposed triumph over death, becomes a source of horror and alienation for the working class. The man’s original identity- Black husband and father- is erased and replaced by a foreign body, severing the physical connection with his family and terrorizing his child. This serves as a potent example of how the poor are denied dignity, with their very bodies being subject to the impersonal and budget-driven mechanics of the justice system. The stack is holy and the sleeve is profane in this techno-future. Technology, in this

setting, enshrines the mind while desecrating flesh and so enables the commodification of death, selectively suspended or forced.

Bodies as Capital: Disposable, Rented and Violated

In *Altered Carbon*, bodies have become interchangeable goods in a digital capitalist society rather than distinct individual identification. These sleeves are rented, purchased, sold and stolen, therefore turning embodiment into a kind of property. People who cannot afford nice sleeves are forced into whatever is available, as Kovacs notes: “The Harlan’s World ethnic mix is primarily Slavic and Japanese, although you can get any variant tank-grown at a price” (Morgan 51). “Here, every face was a different cast and colour—I saw tall, angular-boned Africans, Mongols, pasty-skinned Nordics and, once, a girl that looked like Virginia Vidaura, but I lost her in the crowd” (Morgan 51). These lines illustrate the variety of available bodies and imply that choice is a luxury, contrasting the diverse, multi-ethnic earth with Kovacs's more homogenous home world where specific variants come ‘at a price’. Morgan shows here how the most impoverished groups of society lose their physical autonomy under a thanatopolitical system whereby capital decides death and re-embodiment.

This commodification is especially harsh in its treatment of weak bodies, particularly those of women, immigrants and inmates. This violence is shown in the story of Lizzie Elliot, who was cruelly murdered as her father describes- “She didn’t die, mister. Someone killed her. Someone took a razor and cut her up” (Morgan 92), but she could not be resleeved because of economic hardship. Meanwhile, her mother Irene Elliott was in storage as a prostitute, says- “Bullshit. Lizzie’s ma’s in the store” (Morgan 99) and later she was resleeved in a new body- “The shock of the mirror was written into her new face” (Morgan 321). These resleeving systems sometimes happens without permission after death which brings psychological scars

from trauma. The novel also delves into the sinister repercussions of “Virtual torture programmes” (Morgan 187) and digital abuse, particularly at the Wei Clinic, where Kovacs undergoes brutal virtual interrogation. This software penetrates the subconscious, causing psychological damage with actual, long-term consequences. The virtual is made a locus of bodily violation, collapsing the line between virtuality and embodiment and illustrating how power is extended into the mind through technologically mediated cruelty. According to Braidotti's *The Posthuman*, “bodies are reduced to their informational substrate in terms of materiality and vital capacity. By implication, this means that the markers for the organisation and distribution of differences are now located in micro instances of vital materiality, like the cells of living organisms and the genetic codes of entire species” (97). This states that the flesh itself is turned into a surface for inscription by powerful forces when the body becomes only a passive receiver of informational coding.

The use of convicts as sleeve labour increases this necro-capitalist system even further. Criminals are kept electronically for years or even centuries while their bodies are rented or sold, a process alarmingly comparable to neo-slavery. The re-sleeving of a Latina grandmother into the body of a white man for budgetary reasons during her ‘resurrection’ at church captures this violation of bodily identity and dignity, as states- “stooped, middle-aged white man” (Morgan 261), which powerfully illustrates the violation of identity and the trauma inflicted by this technology on the less privileged. Capitalist posthumanism, as Haraway asserts- “in a sense, organisms have ceased to exist as objects of knowledge, giving way to biotic components, i.e. special kinds of information-processing devices” (149-181). This shows breaks of the body into pieces, units and codes, therefore making embodiment a fragmented, manageable arena for corporate control.

Posthuman Identity and the Ethics of Consciousness

In *Altered Carbon*, the decoupling of the mind from the body subverts the traditional notions of identity, embodiment and soul. With the discovery of cortical stacks, subjectivity is detached from flesh and human identity is redefined as a removable data set. Far from freeing people, though, this virtual ascendance disperses them. As Kovacs comments after sharing a new sleeve: “Nearly two decades I’ve been doing this, and it still jars me to look into the glass and see a total stranger staring back” (Morgan 16). Suggesting a disconnect between his inner self (consciousness) and the physical form he's inhabiting. The digital immortality and body-swapping may preserve consciousness, however they deeply destabilize identity, embodiment and the experience of being fully human highlighted by Kovacs-: “As I dressed in the mirror that night, I suffered the hard-edged conviction that someone else was wearing my sleeve and that I had been reduced to the role of a passenger in the observation car behind the eyes” (Morgan 127). When his new body acts on its own, Kovacs feels betrayed: “Feeling oddly betrayed by my new sleeve, I put the packet away” (Morgan 46). Such a splitting of body and mind is an expression of the posthuman subject's ontological crisis.

This crisis is directly connected to N. Katherine Hayle’s definition of the posthuman as a creature whose existence is not in the body but in information. In *How We Became Posthuman*, Hayles states: “the posthuman view privileges informational pattern over material instantiation, so that embodiment in a biological substrate is seen as an accident of history rather than an inevitability of life.....and most important, by these and other means, the posthuman view configures human being so that it can be seamlessly articulated with intelligent machines. In the posthuman, there are no essential differences or absolute demarcations between bodily existence and computer simulation, cybernetic mechanism and biological or organism, robot teleology and human goals” (2,3). This shows that consciousness is an epiphenomenon and embodiment is secondary to the informational pattern. *Altered Carbon* uncovers this devaluation of embodiment through the ease with which bodies are replaced,

overwritten or deleted. The re-sleeving capacity creates existential instability where the self is no longer anchored in flesh continuity but data replicability. Kovacs, having lived in several sleeves- various races, ages and genders- becomes a fragmented identity, a “ghost in the machine” trying to come to terms with his previous selves and his present self. The novel consistently illustrates Kovacs's fractured identity as a result of his extensive experience with re-sleeving. The experience of psychological fragmentation is described directly: “Psychoentirety rejection, they call it. Or just fragmenting. It’s not unusual to get some tremors, even when you’re an experienced sleeve-changer, but this was the worst case I’d had for years” (Morgan 127).

Rosi Braidotti posits that in posthuman environments, subjectivity is a process of assembling, disassembling and reassembling across multiple axes. As Braidotti theorizes “Becoming-posthuman consequently is a process of redefining one’s sense of attachment and connection to a shared world, a territorial space: urban, social, psychic, ecological, planetary as it may be. It expresses multiple ecologies of belonging, while it enacts the transformation of one’s sensorial and perceptual co-ordinates, in order to acknowledge the collective nature and outward-bound direction of what we still call the self. This is in fact a moveable assemblage within a common life-space that the subject never masters nor possesses but merely inhabits, crosses, always in a community, a pack, a group or a cluster” (193). Kovacs is the paradigm of such a process, when temporarily placed in a female sleeve during a virtual interrogation, Kovacs notes the profound difference in sensory experience: “To be a woman was a sensory experience beyond the male. Touch and texture ran deeper, an interface with environment that male flesh seemed to seal out instinctively” (Morgan 141). This shows his self-subject to technological mediation and social scrutiny more than any constitutive self.

This destabilisation even reaches the artificial intelligence, the sentient hotel AI featured in this novel is named ‘The Hendrix’. It is an advanced AI that achieved “artificial

intelligence status and bought itself out” (Morgan 59), indicating a level of autonomy. The hotel exhibits complex behaviours, such as a ‘hard-wired’ desire for customers that is compared to a human sex drive, and it makes independent, albeit logical, decisions to protect its guest (Kovacs) with lethal force. It also conducts deep background checks on Kovacs and makes sophisticated judgments about his needs. Despite this high level of sentience, its existence is governed by a UN charter “hardwired into my systems” (Morgan 349), and it fears the police as much as a human. The character of Hendrix can undoubtedly be used to explore posthuman ethics and the legal and social status of non-human consciousness. It is a character that upholds posthuman ethics, transgressing anthropocentric conceptions of life and consciousness. Cyborg Manifesto by Donna Haraway is especially relevant here: she argues, “troubling dualisms are self/other, mind/body, culture/nature, male/female, civilized/primitive, reality/appearance, whole/part, agent/resource, maker/ made, active/passive, right/wrong, truth/illusion, total/partial, God/man. The self is the One who is not dominated, who knows that by the service of the other, the other is the one who holds the future, who knows that by the experience of domination, which gives the lie to the autonomy of the self” (149-181).

Therefore, *Altered Carbon* lays bare how posthuman futures never guarantee freedom but reinforce hierarchies and crises of identity, especially for those who cannot afford stable embodiments. Consciousness in the absence of a stable or valued body becomes an unstable condition, raising important questions on personhood, ethics and the value of life in digital capitalism.

Dystopia Now: *Altered Carbon* as Political Allegory

Though *Altered Carbon* is set hundreds of years in the future, its political ideas connect closely to present-day fears. It offers a way to grasp today’s systems of control, especially concerning race, class, surveillance and the commercialisation of life. Achille Mbembe notes

in his essay, Necropolitics, states- “But under what practical conditions is the right to kill, to allow to live, or to expose to death exercised? Who is the subject of this right?” (12). This underscores the point: modern sovereign power extends beyond biopolitical regulation into the authority to expose populations to death- not just to manage life, but to impose vulnerability and mortality. This necropolitical logic runs through *Altered Carbon*, where bodies are not just discarded but moved around as tools of control.

The forced re-sleeving of prisoners, the trafficking of bodies and the digital torture of sex workers mirror real issues, from the prison-industrial complex to data capitalism, biopiracy, and technological colonisation. In one of the most shocking scenes, Lizzie Elliot worked in ‘biocabins’ before she was murdered, which involved a form of virtual or disembodied sexual service. The biocabin experience is described when Kovacs visits Jerry's: “...a body thudded against the frosted glass ahead with an abruptness that made me twitch” (Morgan 98). This scenario highlights the non-consensual exploitation seen in modern trafficking and data extraction systems.

Shoshana Zuboff, in *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism*, argues “human experience is subjugated to surveillance capitalism’s market mechanisms and rendered as ‘behavior’” (15). This statement warns that digital systems turn human experiences into products and make privacy irrelevant. *Altered Carbon* imagines a world where surveillance reaches even the soul- where human minds can be scanned, recorded, questioned and changed. In this setting, digital immortality becomes not freedom but heightened exposure to control. *Altered Carbon* does not only predict a dystopian future but it reveals a dystopian present as well. As Mbembe writes, ‘necropower’ in neoliberal systems often hides behind techno-progressivism while continuing to sort, exploit and discard bodies- “instrumentalization of human existence” (14). The novel shows that these thanatopolitical systems aren’t new they are now mediated through algorithms, data and digitized consciousness.

Conclusion:

Altered Carbon transcends the boundaries of conventional cyberpunk by offering a sharp critique of the posthuman condition under necropolitical regimes. Through its depiction of sleeving, cortical stacks and class-based access to digital immortality, the novel exposes the violent mechanisms through which power sorts, commodifies and discards bodies. The concept that ‘real death’ has become a fate primarily for the poor and that life can be extended indefinitely for the rich is a core theme.

This research paper has posited that *Altered Carbon* is a speculative allegory of the thanatopolitical regimes of contemporary time, in which power is less about the sustaining of life and more about who gets to die and how. Following Achille Mbembe's necropolitics, Zuboff's surveillance capitalism, Braidotti's posthuman, Agamben's bare life and the other theorists, the analysis reveals how the novel mirrors and amplifies actual control mechanisms, from the prison-industrial complex to the commodification of consciousness. Here, technology doesn't emancipate but amplifies inequality- it produces new hierarchies of pain. When digital souls are uploaded and stored, the flesh becomes superfluous, but only for affluent individuals. The poor are hyper-material, disposable and mortal, subject to a cycle of re-sleeving, coercion and violence. Death, therefore, is not an end, but a means of subordination.

Finally, *Altered Carbon* challenges us to consider how far the world has gone toward such a reality. Its dystopia is not predictive of what will be, but reflective of what is already occurring within surveillance systems, racialized law enforcement, labor exploitation and disposability of the body. As literature, it compels readers to ask: Who gets to die with dignity? Who remains trapped in recycled suffering? And what does it mean to be human when the self can be sold, stacked or stolen? In these questions lie the core of our posthuman anxieties- and the future we are already coding into being.

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